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Executive Summary of White Paper (5000 character limit)

Multi-messenger astronomy is currently entering a golden era of discovery. Our new abilities to detect individual sources using combinations of electromagnetic emission, gravitational waves, and cosmic neutrinos enable novel probes of matter at extreme densities, the origin of the elements, and the acceleration of cosmic rays. Over the next decade, the pace of multi-messenger discoveries will rapidly accelerate, thanks to planned upgrades to current GW detectors and new GW facilities that will come online. For several classes of new GW sources (e.g., core collapse supernovae), additional multi-messenger observations of neutrinos may be expected. The Canadian multi-messenger astrophysics community has reached a critical mass, and is well-poised to take a leadership role in upcoming landmark discoveries. Our efforts will utilize new Canadian telescope facilities that are scheduled to come online over the next decade such as JWST, LSST, TMT, SKA, and CASTOR. These new facilities will enable multi-messenger studies of GW events at progressively larger distances, in lockstep with planned sensitivity upgrades to GW detectors. However, challenges await, and we make recommendations that will ensure Canadian leadership in the next breakthrough discoveries in this burgeoning field.

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1 Introduction

Multi-messenger astrophysics is entering a golden era of discovery, in which we can probe the Universe using multiple ‘cosmic messengers’: electromagnetic emission, gravitational waves, and neutrinos. Each individual messenger offers a unique window into the astrophysics of the source, and detections through multiple messengers compounds these rich insights. Several landmark discoveries have been made over just the past two years, including (1) the first detection of both electromagnetic emission and gravitational waves (GWs) from the neutron star merger GW170817 (Abbott et al., 2017c), and (2) the first detection of both electromagnetic emission and high-energy neutrinos from the blazar TXS 0506+056 (IceCube Collaboration et al., 2018a,b). Multi-messenger observations of these two sources have provided transformative insights into a myriad of fundamental questions in astrophysics, including the origin of the heaviest elements (Kasen et al., 2017), the expansion rate of the Universe (Abbott et al., 2017a), and the acceleration of cosmic rays (Keivani et al., 2018). These breakthroughs relied on our ability to search for and localize the electromagnetic counterpart to the gravitational wave or neutrino source using telescopes across all wavelengths. Thanks to new GW detectors, neutrino experiments, and telescope facilities that are scheduled to come online over the next decade, multi-messenger discoveries will occur at an accelerating pace.

Key sensitivity upgrades to current GW and neutrino detectors, along with the additions of new detectors that are planned to come online in the next decade, promise to make multi-messenger discoveries a daily occurrence. The Advanced Laser Interferometer Gravitational-wave Observatory (LIGO) detectors have been in full science operations since 2015. Advanced LIGO has since undergone a progressive series of hardware upgrades to improve the sensitivity of the two detectors, each followed by an extended Observing Run (see Figure 1; Abbott, 2018). During Observing Run 1 (O1), LIGO detected the first black hole–black hole (BH–BH) merger, and during O2, LIGO and the Virgo GW detector in Europe discovered the first neutron star–neutron star (NS–NS) merger. LIGO and Virgo are currently undertaking O3 until April 2020, and the Kamioka Gravitational Wave Detector (KAGRA) in Japan is expected to join the run in early 2020. Advanced LIGO and Advanced Virgo are expected to reach full design sensitivity for O4 in 2021–2022, and then undergo the approved LIGO A+ and Virgo AdV+ upgrades for O5 beginning in 2024 (Miller et al., 2015). At the same time, KARGA will continue to increase in sensitivity and the new LIGO-India detector will join the global network in the mid-2020’s. The addition of these new detectors will dramatically improve the sky localizations of NS–NS mergers to a median of $<20 \text{ deg}^2$ from the current $\sim 200 \text{ deg}^2$. In the late 2020’s, the LIGO Voyager upgrade will extend the detection horizon for NS–NS mergers (with likely electromagnetic counterparts) by a factor of ~ 6 over O3 (Reitze et al., 2019), which corresponds to a factor of ~ 200 increase from the current the detection volume and rate. Furthermore, construction of proposed new 3rd-generation GW detector facilities, including the Cosmic Explorer and Einstein Telescope, are expected to begin. In all, these major infrastructure developments for GW detection will lead to orders-of-magnitude more multi-messenger discoveries over the next decade, and represent a timely opportunity for strategic Canadian investment.

For several classes of GW sources, additional multi-messenger detection of neutrinos may be expected. Neutrino experiments had previously detected thermal MeV neutrinos from the supernova SN1987A (Bahcall et al., 1987), which provided our first multi-messenger view of the core-collapse process, and lead to the formation of the SuperNova Early Warning System (SNEWS) for rapid dissemination of neutrino detections. Current experiments such as the Helium and Lead Observatory (HALO) and SNO+ at SNOLAB, as well as future facilities like the next-generation Enriched Xenon Observatory (nEXO) and HALO-1kT, will ensure Canada has a prominent role in multi-messenger astrophysics from the next Galactic supernova. At high energies ($\gtrsim \text{TeV}$), the IceCube experiment has detected diffuse cosmic high-energy neutrinos since 2013 (IceCube Collaboration, 2013), and identified the first individual source through multi-messenger observations of the flaring blazar TXS 0506+056 in 2017 (IceCube Collaboration et al., 2018a,b). However, modeling has shown that blazars can account for only $\lesssim 10\%$ of the diffuse cosmic high-energy neutrinos, and thus their origin will be unveiled through future multi-messenger detections of new sources using planned upgrades to current detectors such as the IceCube Upgrade, Astronomy with a Neutrino Telescope and Abyss environmental RESearch (ANTARES), and Cubic Kilometre Neutrino Telescope (KM3NeT), along with proposed next-generation facilities such as IceCube-Gen2 and the Pacific Ocean Neutrino Explorer (P-ONE) off the coast of British Columbia. These multi-messenger neutrino detection efforts also offer a unique opportunity for novel collaborations between the Canadian astronomical and high-energy physics communities.

Figure 1: **Timeline of gravitational wave detector capabilities over the next decade.** LIGO and Virgo will undergo progressive sensitivity upgrades that improve its detection horizon to NS-NS mergers well beyond the current 120 Mpc in Observing Run 3. Furthermore, new facilities such as KAGRA in Japan and LIGO-India will come online, dramatically improving the GW localizations. Beyond 2026, the LIGO A+ upgrade will extend the NS-NS detection horizon to ~ 660 Mpc, and 3rd-generation GW facilities such as the Cosmic Explorer and Einstein Telescope will begin construction. Figure from Abbott (2018).

The Canadian multi-messenger astrophysics community has now reached a critical mass, and is well-poised to take a leadership role in upcoming landmark discoveries thanks to the fortuitous timing of new Canadian telescope development over the next decade. The Canadian Coalition for Multi-Messenger Astrophysics has established Target-of-Opportunity (ToO) observational programs on various Canadian telescope facilities (e.g., Gemini and CFHT) in LIGO/Virgo O3, and collaborative programs are beginning to be established with Canadian GW scientists inside the LIGO Collaboration, as well as connections to the strong Canadian experimental neutrino community. Over the next decade, these efforts will expand towards next-generation telescope facilities with significant Canadian participation, including the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST), Large Synoptic Survey Telescope (LSST), Square Kilometer Array (SKA), Thirty Meter Telescope (TMT), and Cosmological Advanced Survey Telescope for Optical and ultraviolet Research (CASTOR). The timing of these new facilities will enable multi-messenger studies of GW events at progressively larger distances over the next decade, in lockstep with planned sensitivity upgrades to GW detectors. In this white paper, we lay out a roadmap for Canadian leadership in the next breakthrough discoveries in multi-messenger astrophysics, focusing on new horizons enabled by Canadian telescope facilities.

2 Science Motivation and Key Questions

Electromagnetic follow-up of GW events has garnered intense interest world-wide subsequent to the breakthrough discovery of NS-NS merger GW170817. We focus our discussion on key questions that can be addressed with current and next-generation Canadian telescope facilities. Telescope observations of GW170817 detected emission across the electromagnetic spectrum that was broadly consistent with our theoretical expectations of NS-NS mergers, but also raised a plethora of new questions. Intensive imaging and spectroscopy of the optical/infrared emission confirmed that the merger expelled neutron-rich ejecta that produced a bright ‘kilonova’, powered by the formation and radioactive decay of r -process elements in the ejecta material (e.g., Drout et al., 2017). Contemporaneously, Gamma-ray telescopes detected a short GRB from the merger, and X-ray/radio follow-up observations revealed synchrotron afterglow emission that brightened over several months, indicative of an off-axis relativistic jet (e.g., Haggard et al., 2017; Ruan et al., 2018). Despite the stunningly rich scientific insights from this single event, GW170817 also challenged our understanding of the detailed astrophysics of compact object mergers, and now strongly motivate multi-messenger observations of a large sample of new events in the next decade. Below, we discuss several key science questions that focus primarily on the UV/optical/IR wavelengths. Additional science questions and discussion of GW follow-up in the radio are provided in complementary LRP 2020 white papers by V. Kaspi (E049, focusing broadly on radio transients) and K. Spekkens (E042, focusing specifically on the SKA).

(1) What powers kilonovae? Kilonovae can be powered by combinations of a variety of different energy sources, leading to a wide diversity in model predictions. Although both optical/infrared imaging and spectroscopy of the GW170817 kilonova suggested that its emission was dominated by the decay of freshly-synthesized r -process elements in the ejecta material (e.g., Chornock et al., 2017; Drout et al., 2017; Shappee et al., 2017; Kilpatrick et al., 2017), additional model complexities are required to explain its puzzling colour evolution. The multi-

Figure 2: **Current and future Canadian telescope facilities are well-suited for follow-up of GW events.** Left: The multi-band UV/optical/NIR light curve of GW170817, displaying thermal emission with an early peak in the UV before cooling into the IR over ~ 10 days. Right: The multi-epoch optical/NIR spectra of GW170817, displaying clear features indicative of r -process nucleosynthesis. A suite of Canadian telescope facilities that can observe all aspects of the kilonova are also shown. The large aperture sizes of these telescopes are necessary to detect the faint kilonova counterparts of GW events at large distances in the next decade. Complementary radio observations of relativistic jets launched by the merger can be provided by the SKA (see discussions in white papers E042 and E049). Figure adapted from Drout et al. (2017); Pian et al. (2017).

band light curves (see Figure 2) revealed early blue UV emission that cooled to red IR emission over timescales of ~ 10 days, which has been suggested to be due to (1) a combination of ejecta material from different origins with different ejecta masses and velocities (e.g., Kasen et al., 2017), (2) ejecta from a single origin but with a time-varying opacity as the ejecta cools (Waxman et al., 2018), and/or (3) wind ejecta from a hypermassive magnetar remnant that collapsed into a black hole at timescales of < 1 sec post-merger (Metzger et al., 2018). Since the predicted colour evolution of the kilonova from these different scenarios is dependent on various binary parameters that can be estimated from the GW waveform (e.g., binary inclination, mass ratio, and mass of the compact remnant, see Figure 3), multi-messenger observations of a *sample* of NS-NS mergers (each with different binary parameters) are urgently needed to test these models of kilonova emission. For the faint kilonovae from distant mergers that will be detected through GWs in the next decade, these tests require ToO imaging on large-aperture wide-field UV and optical telescopes to quickly discover the faint counterparts of distant mergers, and 5-meter class telescopes to obtain multi-band light curves of the fading optical/IR emission over the subsequent 10 days.

(2) **What is the origin of the r -process elements in the Universe?** It is still highly unclear whether kilonovae from NS-NS mergers can produce *all* of the r -process elements in the Universe (e.g., Côté et al., 2019; Siegel

Figure 3: **Kilonovae are expected to display a wide diversity in their emission properties, depending on various parameters of the merging binary.** Various model scenario for kilonova from NS-NS merger producing a stable NS remnant (left), NS-NS merger producing a BH remnant (centre), and NS-BH mergers (right) are shown. Each scenario produces different blue/UV and red/IR emission, depending on parameters such as viewing angle, the mass ratio of the binary, and the nature of the remnant. Multi-messenger observations of a sample of kilonovae in the next decade will disentangle the dependence of the electromagnetic emission on the properties of the binary as inferred from GWs. Figure from Kasen et al. (2017).

Figure 4: **NIR spectroscopy of kilonovae probes the yields and abundances pattern of r -process elements produced in NS-NS mergers.** The Gemini NIR spectrum of GW170817 (black) displays features that are broadly consistent with model predictions from r -process nucleosynthesis (red), with a lanthanide element fraction of 10^{-2} . Similar NIR spectroscopy of a sample of kilonovae can probe the diversity in the r -process element yields and abundance patterns, thus determining whether NS-NS mergers are the origin of all the r -process elements in the Universe. Figure from Chornock et al. (2017).

et al., 2019, also see white paper E057). The smoking-gun signature of r -process nucleosynthesis in kilonovae is the spectral features in their optical/NIR spectra, which were broadly consistent with theoretical predictions for GW170817 (see Figure 4). However, it is unknown whether the yield and abundance pattern of r -process elements produced by GW170817 is representative of all kilonovae, or if different kilonovae will produce different amounts of r -process elements with different abundance patterns. In particular, simulations predict that both the ejecta masses and abundance patterns in different NS-NS mergers will depend sensitively on the binary parameters (e.g., mass ratio, and mass of the compact remnant) in ways that are not yet tested (e.g., Hotokezaka et al., 2013). A full accounting of the origin of r -process elements in the Universe will also require multi-messenger observations of a *sample* of NS-NS mergers, to determine the diversity of both their r -process yields and abundance patterns, and test how this depends on the binary parameters. Answering this major science question requires ToO optical and NIR spectroscopy on large-aperture telescopes once a kilonova counterpart to a GW event has been localized.

(3) What are other sources of gravitational waves? LIGO/Virgo has thus far confidently detected GWs from many BH-BH mergers and a NS-NS merger, and landmark discoveries of other sources of GWs are expected over the next decade. For example, NS-BH mergers are also expected to produce kilonovae, and a multi-messenger detection is inevitable. Models suggest that kilonovae from NS-BH mergers will also be primarily powered by radioactive decay of r -process nuclei synthesized by the ejecta, but with key differences in comparison to NS-NS mergers (e.g., Fernández et al., 2017). The lack of a surface on the BH implies that NS-BH mergers will not

produce shocked ejecta at the merger interface, which suggests that kilonovae from NS-BH mergers may be redder in colour and rise in luminosity later after the merger. Furthermore, the extreme tidal forces from the BH can tidally deform and disrupt the NS prior to the merger, which will imprint a signature in GWs, emit distinct electromagnetic emission, and enable new tests of general relativity (Foucart et al., 2013). These insights on new classes of GW sources will require ToO UV/optical imaging programs on wide-field large-aperture telescopes to search for a counterpart, ToO optical/NIR imaging programs on moderate-aperture telescopes to photometrically monitor the fading counterpart, and ToO optical/NIR spectroscopy on large-aperture telescopes for spectroscopic monitoring. Aside from NS-BH mergers, nearby spinning pulsars are expected to emit nearly continuous GWs. Observations by Canadian radio facilities such as SKA will make them prime multi-messenger targets for the discovery of a new type of GW emission, which will probe the density and structure of neutron stars (also see white paper E042).

(4) Can we detect sources with three cosmic messengers? Core-collapse supernovae (CCSNe) are predicted to be detectable sources of both GWs and neutrinos, but a GW detection has not yet been achieved. CCSNe simulations suggest that oscillations in the proto-NS and turbulent instabilities in the accreting material during the collapse will produce GWs that are currently detectable for CCSNe in the Milky Way at rates of 1-2 per century (Gossan et al., 2016). Using 3rd-generation GW detectors in the 2030's, CCSNe may be detectable at similar rates beyond the Milky Way, although these calculations depend sensitively on the poorly-understood physics of the core collapse process. Furthermore, the bulk of core's gravitational binding energy is extracted through emission of thermal MeV neutrinos, as previously detected in SN1987A (e.g., Bahcall et al., 1987; Burrows & Lattimer, 1987). High-energy (GeV-TeV) neutrinos can also be produced in CCSNe through cosmic rays accelerated in the supernova shock, or outflows from a central engine. A joint detection of a Galactic CCSN in electromagnetic emission, GWs, and neutrinos would thus be a rosetta stone for our understanding of their core collapse process. This CCSN would likely be bright enough to be accessible to 1m-class telescopes, but observations will be highly competitive and would require ToO programs coordinated with GW and neutrino facilities to ensure priority.

3 Canada's Unique Position in Multi-Messenger Astrophysics

The Canadian astronomical community is uniquely-positioned to take a leadership role in multi-messenger astrophysics over the next decade due to an auspicious confluence of several factors, including a favorable coalition-building environment, fortuitous timing of new Canadian telescope facilities, and a critical mass of key personnel. In Section 3.1 below, we first summarize the current Canadian multi-messenger astrophysics landscape, and in Section 3.2, we detail a roadmap for Canadian leadership in the next decade.

3.1 Past and Current Canadian Involvement in Multi-Messenger Astrophysics

Previously in LIGO/Virgo O2, Canadian scientists led key multi-messenger studies of the NS-NS merger GW170817. These efforts included the initial discovery and characterization of the GW signal (Abbott et al., 2017b), the discovery of the UV/optical/NIR kilonova counterpart using various ground-based telescopes that indicated the presence of r -process nucleosynthesis in the merger ejecta (Drout et al., 2017), *Chandra* X-ray observations of the synchrotron afterglow of the short GRB that suggested the launching of an off-axis relativistic jet (Haggard et al., 2017; Ruan et al., 2018; Nynka et al., 2018), and numerical relativity simulations of NS-NS mergers that provided the template GW waveforms used to detect the merger. These efforts were independent and did not use any Canadian telescope facilities, primarily because the key personnel were new to the Canada astronomy community. Subsequent to GW170817, the Canadian multi-messenger astrophysics community has now reached a critical mass, lead by permanent faculty members playing key roles in GW follow-up observations in the UV/optical/IR (Drout) and X-ray/radio (Haggard, Spekkens), modeling of kilonova remnants (Safi-Harb), LIGO instrumentation and GW data analysis (McIver), along with theorists working on the astrophysics of compact object mergers (East, Lehner, Siegel, Fernandez). This multi-messenger expertise from the GW side is complemented by deep expertise in neutrino detection (Brunner, Chen, Grant, Prio, Virtue, Yanez) from a wide array of neutrino experiments, and theorists working on multi-messenger neutrino astrophysics (Caballero).

	LIGO Gravitational Wave Detector Capabilities		Facilities to search for counterparts to GW events		Facilities to photometrically monitor counterparts to GW events		Facilities to spectroscopically monitor counterparts to GW events	
	NS-NS merger detection horizon	Kilonova peak optical/NIR magnitude	UV imaging search	Optical imaging search	Optical photometric monitoring	NIR photometric monitoring	Optical spectroscopic monitoring	NIR spectroscopic monitoring
Early 2020's	175 Mpc	21 mag		CFHT, LSST	CFHT, LSST	CFHT, Gemini	Gemini	Gemini, JWST
Mid 2020's	330 Mpc	22 mag		LSST	LSST	Gemini	Gemini	Gemini, JWST
Late 2020's	~660 Mpc	24 mag	CASTOR	LSST	LSST	Gemini, TMT	TMT	JWST

Figure 5: A possible suite of Canadian telescope facilities well-suited for follow-up of GW events in the next decade. The peak magnitude of an electromagnetic counterpart at each detection horizon assumes a GW170817-like kilonova, although kilonovae may be significantly fainter depending on the exact parameters of the merger.

Currently in LIGO/Virgo O3, Canadian scientists have now united to form a Canadian Coalition for Multi-Messenger Astrophysics, and have begun to leverage Canadian access to current telescope facilities to establish ToO programs for GW follow-up. Although the formation of this coalition was first and foremost motivated by a friendly collaborative spirit, it was also necessary due to the highly-competitive environment in this field that developed as a result of GW170817. Specifically, scientists working on follow-up of GW events have increasingly consolidated their efforts into massive collaborations, which now dominate ToO telescope programs on major international telescope facilities. By uniting together, the Canadian Coalition becomes internationally-competitive as the only Canadian-led proposals on international telescope facilities with Canadian partnership. The relatively small size of the Canadian multi-messenger astrophysics community enables this competitive advantage, especially in comparison to the fractured collaborations in the United States all competing for the same telescope allocations.

Our Canadian Coalition has now established a robust suite of approved ToO programs on Canadian telescope facilities to follow-up LIGO/Virgo GW sources in O3. These carefully-designed programs will obtain complementary observations to (1) search for a counterpart to the GW event using wide-field optical imaging on the CFHT telescope; (2) monitor any optical/infrared emission from the counterpart using imaging on the CFHT telescope over two weeks; (3) obtain optical and infrared spectroscopy on the Gemini Observatory telescopes over one week; and (4) perform X-ray and radio monitoring using the *Chandra* X-ray and Jansky VLA radio telescopes over one month. Each of these programs contributes a critical piece to the multi-messenger puzzle of compact object mergers. Furthermore, efforts to foster closer collaboration with the Canadian neutrino community are underway, beginning with the ‘Supernova Neutrinos in the Multi-Messenger Era’ workshop hosted by Laurentian University and SNOLAB in June 2019, and a Canadian multi-messenger astrophysics workshop to be held at McGill University in early 2020 with support from the MacDonal Institute.

3.2 Future Canadian Leadership in Multi-Messenger Astrophysics in the 2020's

Over the next decade, our Canadian Coalition for Multi-Messenger Astrophysics will continue and further expand our program to follow-up GW sources, although new challenges await. Unlike GW170817, the vast majority of compact object mergers discovered by the sensitive GW detectors in the 2020's will be at significantly larger distances (Abbott, 2018), with counterparts that are correspondingly much fainter. For example, the LIGO A+ upgrade will detect NS-NS mergers out to 330 Mpc during O5 beginning in 2024, while the LIGO Voyager upgrade will reach ~660 Mpc beginning in 2027. A GW170817-like kilonova counterpart would *peak* at $\gtrsim 22$ and $\gtrsim 24$ mag at these respective distances before fading. Thus, next-generation large-aperture telescopes will by necessity become the workhorse facilities for multi-messenger GW astrophysics in the next decade.

The timing of new Canadian telescope facilities that will come online in the next decade will enable multi-

messenger studies of GW events at progressive larger distances, and is fortuitously in lock-step with the larger distances probed by planned upgrades to GW detectors over this time-frame. This enables us to use a suite of Canadian telescope facilities to cover all observational requirements for addressing the key science questions outlined in Section 2, including the initial search for a kilonova counterpart, as well as photometric and spectroscopic monitoring of the localized kilonova during its fading. Figure 5 summarizes the expected LIGO detection horizons for NS-NS mergers in the next decade, and various Canadian telescope facilities that can be available to probe all aspects of a GW170817-like kilonova at those distances. We emphasize that although none of these facilities were specifically designed for multi-messenger astrophysics as their primary scientific goal, the use of this combination of facilities for this program elevates their scientific utility to be greater than the sum of its parts. Below, we describe in more detail how these facilities can be used for GW follow-up.

Early 2020's: In the early 2020's, Advanced LIGO/Virgo will detect GWs from NS-NS mergers out to 175 Mpc in O4, and a GW170817-like kilonova counterpart will peak at ~ 21 mag. At these magnitudes, optical wide-field imaging searches for GW counterparts can be continued with our established ToO programs on the CFHT, before construction of the Maunakea Spectroscopic Explorer (MSE) begins in the mid-2020's. Once a counterpart has been localized, we can continue to use our established ToO programs to perform optical/NIR photometric monitoring using the CFHT and Gemini telescopes, and optical/NIR spectroscopic monitoring using Gemini. Additionally, the coming decade will be a critical time to invest in preparing to build and analyze data from future ground-based and space-based GW detectors. GW astronomers based in Canada will be able to leverage insights from the Canadian collaborative multi-messenger astronomy effort and firmly establish Canada as a key leader in GW astrophysics.

Mid 2020's: In the mid 2020's, LIGO/Virgo A+ will detect GWs from NS-NS mergers out to 330 Mpc in O5, and a GW170817-like kilonova counterpart will peak at ~ 22 mag. CFHT will be closed for construction of the MSE, but optical wide-field imaging searches for GW counterparts can instead be performed with the LSST (science operations scheduled to begin in 2022). A portion of Canadians will have access to proprietary LSST data thanks to buy-ins from the Dunlap Institute and the University of Waterloo's Centre for Astrophysics. LSST is ideal for tiling GW localization regions due to its large aperture, wide field of view, and fast slewing capabilities. However, it will be critical to ensure that LSST establishes support for ToO-mode observations. Once a counterpart has been localized, optical/NIR photometric monitoring can be performed with a combination of the Gemini telescopes and continued LSST observations, while optical spectroscopic monitoring can be performed using the Gemini telescopes. However, spectroscopy of the faint late-time NIR/MIR emission will require large-aperture telescopes such as JWST, which will support ToO programs and begin science operation in the early 2020's.

Late 2020's: In the late 2020's, LIGO Voyager will detect GWs from NS-NS mergers out to ~ 660 Mpc, and a GW170817-like kilonova counterpart will peak at ~ 24 mag. Since GW170817 was observed to first peak in the UV on timescales of < 1 day, the launch of CASTOR enables the new and unique capability to perform wide-field UV imaging searches for GW counterparts. Fortuitously, the addition of new GW detection facilities such as LIGO-India in the late 2020's will improve GW localization of NS-NS mergers to < 20 deg², which can be fully tiled in a reasonable number of pointings using a wide-field telescope such as CASTOR. CASTOR currently plans to devote 5% of its observing time to ToO-mode observations. Contemporaneously, optical imaging searches can be performed with LSST. Once a counterpart has been localized, optical/NIR photometric monitoring of the faint and rapidly-fading kilonova can still be performed with Gemini, but optical/NIR spectroscopy will require large-aperture telescopes such as TMT, which is currently scheduled to see first light in 2028. TMT is particularly well-suited for follow-up spectroscopy of GW counterparts, thanks to its design requirement that observations of any accessible target using any of the instruments must be possible in < 10 minutes, making it unique in comparison to the ELT and GMT. NIR/MIR spectroscopic monitoring will continue to be performed using JWST. Lastly, the SKA will begin science operations, enabling sensitive observations of synchrotron afterglow emission from a relativistic jet launched during the merger (see discussions in white papers E042 and E049). In the 2030's, this ultimate combination of Canadian telescope facilities will still be highly-competitive for follow-up of GWs detected by new 3rd-generation GW facilities such as Cosmic Explorer and Einstein Telescope, which will detect NS-NS mergers to distances of $\sim 27,000$ Mpc ($z \sim 0.17$). Finally, exciting new horizons in multi-messenger astrophysics will emerge with the planned launch of the space-based Laser Interferometer Space Antenna (LISA) GW detector.

4 Recommendations for the LRP 2020

(1) Identify Canadian multi-messenger astrophysics as a key strategic initiative. Although Canada is well-poised to take a leadership role in the next landmark multi-messenger breakthroughs in the next decade, support from the LRP 2020 will be critical. Above, we have outlined how the confluence of GW detectors across the globe and major Canadian telescope facilities coming online over the next decade, along with the critical mass in expertise reached by the Canadian Coalition for Multi-Messenger Astrophysics, will enable this science program to flourish in the next decade. However, challenges await at critical junctures, primarily in successfully securing ToO programs on telescope facilities (such as JWST), hiring of key personnel, support for GW detector observations, and funding for training of students/postdocs. Identifying multi-messenger astrophysics as a key strategic initiative in the LRP 2020 will be a powerful aid as we face these challenges, by demonstrating broad support for this science program from Canadian astronomical community.

(2) Fund and construct the CASTOR space telescope. One critical telescope facility for Canadian multi-messenger astrophysics that is currently not yet funded for construction is CASTOR. CASTOR is uniquely capable of sensitive wide-field UV imaging that can tile the entire $<20 \text{ deg}^2$ localization regions of GW sources in the next decade. This capability is critical for rapid identification of faint kilonovae counterparts, due to their early UV emission that peaks on timescales of $\lesssim 1$ day. Furthermore, CASTOR already plans to devote 5% of its observing time to ToO programs, and GW sources will undoubtedly be amongst the highest-priority science targets.

(3) Ensure ToO capabilities on current and future Canadian telescope facilities. ToO-mode observations are necessary for the science cases we detailed above. For all of the Canadian telescope facilities we discussed, ToO capabilities are planned, and detailed strategies to manage such programs are either already in place (e.g., Gemini, JWST), or still being finalized (e.g., LSST, TMT, CASTOR, SKA). To ensure that Canadian scientists are able to lead ToO-mode observational programs, is imperative that we actively advocate for the ability to propose ToO observations on these Canadian telescope facilities

(4) Support participation in one proposed international MMA-specific telescope facility. The world-wide interest in multi-messenger astrophysics after the discovery of GW170817 has quickly spawned many small space-based telescope concepts specifically designed for multi-messenger and transient astrophysics. These proposed telescopes include STROBE-X and TAP in X-rays, DUET and ULTRASAT in the UV, and SVOM in UV/optical/IR. Given current budget constraints, these telescopes fill more niche scientific goals that are missed by larger general-purpose observatories. We urge that Canada identify a proposed telescope that is complementary to the strengths of Canadian telescope facilities in the 2020's, and invest in joining as an official partner. For example, although Canadian scientists currently lead GW follow-up programs on international facilities such as the *Chandra* X-ray Observatory, participation in a wide-field X-ray telescope optimized for transients can ensure broader Canadian participation in multi-messenger discoveries, and further cement Canadian leadership in this burgeoning field.

1: How does the proposed initiative result in fundamental or transformational advances in our understanding of the Universe?

The rise of multi-messenger astronomy has opened exciting new opportunities to probe extreme astrophysical environments, through joint detections of individual sources in electromagnetic emission, gravitational waves, and neutrinos. Each ‘cosmic messenger’ offers a unique window into the astrophysics of the source, and detections through multiple messengers compounds these rich insights. For example, multi-messenger observations of neutron star merger GW170817 in both electromagnetic emission and gravitational waves has addressed a diverse array of fundamental questions in astrophysics, including the origin of the elements, the expansion rate of the Universe, and new tests of general relativity. Similarly, the detection of the flaring blazar TXS 0506+056 in both high-energy neutrinos and electromagnetic emission is now probing the origin of cosmic rays, and offers unique opportunities for novel collaborations with the high-energy physics community.

2: What are the main scientific risks and how will they be mitigated?

Since the field of multi-messenger gravitational wave and neutrino astrophysics is still emerging, a possible scientific risk is that the poorly-constrained astrophysical rates of events are significantly lower than expected. However, it is more likely that surprising and unexpected discoveries will be made in this nascent field.

3: Is there the expectation of and capacity for Canadian scientific, technical or strategic leadership?

The timing of new Canadian telescope facilities that will come online in the next decade will enable multi-messenger studies of gravitational wave events at progressively larger distances, and is fortuitously in lock-step with the larger distances probed by progressive upgrades to gravitational wave detectors over this timeframe (see Figure 5). This enables us to use a suite of Canadian telescope facilities to cover all observational requirements for addressing the major science questions outlined in Section 2, thus providing an unique opportunity for leadership in this burgeoning field.

4: Is there support from, involvement from, and coordination within the relevant Canadian community and more broadly?

The Canadian multi-messenger astrophysics community has reached a critical mass, and is well-poised to take a leadership role in upcoming landmark discoveries. Previously in LIGO/Virgo Observing Run 2, Canadian scientists led key multi-messenger studies of the neutron star merger GW170817. Subsequent to that breakthrough, Canadian scientists have now united to form a Canadian Coalition for Multi-Messenger Astrophysics, and have begun leveraging Canadian access to current telescope facilities to establish target-of-opportunity programs for gravitational wave follow-up. Over the next decade, these efforts will expand towards new Canadian telescope facilities, as well as closer collaboration with the gravitational wave and neutrino communities.

5: Will this program position Canadian astronomy for future opportunities and returns in 2020-2030 or beyond 2030?

Our recommendation for the LRP 2020 are critical for ensuring that this science program will flourish over the next decade. Furthermore, the possible suite of Canadian telescope facilities that can be available for multi-messenger astrophysics at the end of this decade will continue to be well-suited for follow-up of events detected by third-generation gravitational wave detectors in the 2030's such as the Cosmic Explorer and Einstein Telescope, as well as the space-based Laser Interferometer Space Antenna (LISA).

6: In what ways is the cost-benefit ratio, including existing investments and future operating costs, favourable?

Upcoming next-generation telescope facilities with significant Canadian participation (e.g., JWST, LSST, TMT, CASTOR, SKA) are already well-suited for follow-up of gravitational wave events at increasingly larger distances over the next decade. Furthermore, since none of these facilities were specifically designed for multi-messenger astrophysics as their primary scientific goal, the use of these facilities for this science program is not only highly cost effective, but also elevates their scientific utility to be greater than the sum of its parts.

7: What are the main programmatic risks and how will they be mitigated?

The main programmatic risk for multi-messenger astrophysics is the availability of various gravitational wave, neutrino, and telescope facilities over the next decade. Funding and support for gravitational wave and neutrino experiments such as LIGO and IceCube are secure until at least the mid-2020's, and next-generation facilities like Cosmic Voyager and P-ONE slated for the late-2020's are still in their proposal stages. For multi-messenger observations, new telescope facilities with Canadian participation such as TMT and LSST will ideally stay on schedule to enable follow-up of the faint counterparts to more distant gravitational wave and neutrino events that will be detected in the next decade. In the event that there are significant delays, continued participation in versatile facilities such as the Gemini Observatory will mitigate some of these risks.

8: Does the proposed initiative offer specific tangible benefits to Canadians, including but not limited to interdisciplinary research, industry opportunities, HQP training, EDI, outreach or education?

Multi-messenger astrophysics offers unique opportunities for collaboration between the Canadian astronomical and high-energy physics communities.

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